

Empowering Europe's Edge: SMEs Driving Innovation in Energy and Robotics

Best practice category

New impetus for chips design

Stakeholder group

SMEs and start-ups

Value chain position

R&D

General Information

Logiicdev is a SME founded in 2020 and based in Graz, Austria. Created by experts in the electronics sector, the company specialises in cutting-edge research and development for Edge solutions in the energy and robotics sectors, with over 20 years of experience in power electronics, embedded software and semiconductors, as well as constantly updating its knowledge of emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, 5G and cybersecurity.

The team at Logiicdev are experts in field-programmable gate arrays (FPGAs), which are programmable chips extremely versatile that allow developers to test variables even after the board is built, by uploading new configuration files that enable updated functionality. For instance, when developing basic systems, testing is essential, and programmable chips are used for evaluation and validation purposes. Logiicdev develops and provides both the hardware and the platform to support this process.

Activities and best practices

- Logiicdev is a member of networks such as ANAS and EPOS, which play an important role in fostering collaboration, knowledge sharing, and technological advancement within the European innovation ecosystem. By participating in these associations, Logiicdev aims to actively contribute to joint initiatives, stay aligned with strategic developments in the sector, and promote the visibility and engagement of SMEs in the broader R&D landscape. Membership in such platforms also supports the company's commitment to strengthening connections between research, industry, and emerging technologies.
- Logiicdev develops custom FPGA-based IP solutions designed as flexible, low-cost alternatives to Application-Specific Integrated Circuits (ASICs), reducing development time and hidden costs. This ability allows partner companies to test and validate complex architectures quickly, contributing to the diffusion of advanced technologies even in contexts with limited resources.

- With OmniPower, Logiicdev has developed a patented motherboard designed exclusively for power applications in power generation, transmission, storage and consumption. Equipped with AI capability, the platform enables leak-free two-way operation, real-time monitoring and integration of digital twin technologies to optimise predictive analysis and battery management. This solution, developed entirely in-house, demonstrates the company's integrated approach, which combines advanced electronic design, energy optimisation and attention to the real needs of industry.

Challenges addressed with this practice

Logiicdev faces critical challenges related to access to advanced testing solutions, rapidity in prototype development, and deployment of complex technologies in resource-constrained settings. Through platforms such as OmniPower and the use of IP over FPGA as an alternative to ASICs, the company helps reduce development time and costs. In this way, it supports SMEs and technology partners in adopting cutting-edge solutions, contributing to the strengthening of the European ecosystem between research and industry.